

THE FUTURE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN MANAGEMENT OF HIGHER EDUCATION

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Аннотация. Ушбу илмий мақолада олий таълим соҳасида самарали бошқарувни таъминлашда сунъий интеллектдан фойдаланиш масалалари атрофлича таҳлилий тадқиқ этилган.

Калит сўзлар: рақамли трансформация, сунъий интеллект, олий таълим, тўртинчи sanoat инқилоби, таълим технологиялари.

Аннотация. В данной научной статье подробно анализируются вопросы использования искусственного интеллекта в организации эффективного управления в сфере высшего образования.

Ключевые слова: цифровая трансформация, искусственный интеллект, высшее образование, промышленная революция, образовательные технологии.

Abstract. In this scientific article, the issues of using artificial intelligence in the organization of effective management in the field of higher education are thoroughly analyzed.

Keywords: digital transformation, artificial intelligence, higher education, industrial revolution, educational technologies.

Modern society strives to create more intelligent, adaptable and energy-efficient systems that interact, detect vulnerabilities and respond to them in real time. The result of the evolutionary development of technologies was the fourth industrial revolution, in which one of the key places is given to artificial intelligence.

The initiator of introducing the concept of "artificial intelligence" (AI) into scientific circulation was the American scientist John McCarthy. This event occurred about 70 years ago, in the distant 1956. At present, artificial intelligence is called information technology based on intelligent systems and algorithms capable of performing operations that have traditionally been carried out by humans throughout their existence. The main goal of artificial intelligence is the intelligent modeling of achievable mental operations [1].

Artificial intelligence is widely used in various industries, including healthcare, finance, retail, manufacturing, and transportation. The field of education, especially higher education, is no exception. Artificial intelligence is rooted in all levels of education and the implementation of educational programs in higher education institutions.

Искусственный интеллект стал преобразующей силой в высшем образовании, изменив традиционные парадигмы преподавания, усвоения знаний и административных процессов. В настоящее время в Узбекистан идет активное внедрение информационных технологий, основанных на искусственном интеллекте, в процесс подготовки студентов вузов [2].

In the teaching field, AI-powered platforms use advanced algorithms and machine learning techniques to personalize the learning experience. Intelligent systems analyze individual learning patterns, adapting learning content to students' different abilities and needs. AI-powered virtual classrooms facilitate real-time interaction, creating a dynamic and engaging learning

environment. Moreover, AI-powered assessment tools provide timely feedback, helping educators identify areas of improvement and customize learning paths for students [3].

Changes in the learning mechanism directly influence and stimulate the transformation of both the curriculum and the standards of content delivery. This means that the phenomenon of artificial intelligence has led to the formation of intelligent curriculum development, intelligent teaching systems. Artificial intelligence as an educational tool can create a wide range of opportunities for student learning, showing where students make mistakes, what they need to pay attention to, explaining and demonstrating to them where they have knowledge gaps that need special attention, what else they need to learn. Personalized education based on artificial intelligence is a real revolution in terms of how future students will study educational programs in universities. In addition, the personalized approach to learning is expected to increase the average IQ of university students.

The impact of AI extends beyond pedagogy, revolutionizing administrative tasks in higher education institutions. Automated chatbots handle routine student queries, increasing administrative efficiency and responsiveness. Predictive analytics powered by AI assist in enrollment management, retention strategies, and resource allocation, streamlining institutional administrative operations.

Moreover, AI-powered research tools empower scientists by accelerating the pace of discovery and innovation. Natural language processing algorithms analyze vast amounts of text data, helping scientists with literature reviews and knowledge synthesis. AI algorithms also facilitate data-driven decision making, providing insights into institutional performance, student engagement, and program effectiveness.

The use of artificial intelligence for educational initiatives brings countless benefits to both universities and students. Currently, artificial intelligence is actively used in the development of educational materials, in the objective assessment of student work, in the mechanism of communicating the results of student work to students, in monitoring the indicators of physical and mental health of students in various programs. Variability in the course of training provides an opportunity to choose educational services for the student as a real consumer, and each educational organization determines its own path of development [4]. In the future, students can be referred to automated support services managed by artificial intelligence. This will become commonplace.

However, integrating AI into higher education is not without challenges. Ethical concerns regarding data privacy, algorithmic bias, and the displacement of traditional teaching methods require careful consideration today. In addition, improving digital literacy among faculty and students is critical to effectively harnessing the potential of AI.

Artificial intelligence is a technology that has the potential to cause the biggest breakthrough in education. In recent years, digital transformation has been implemented in all sectors of the national economy, but education, especially higher education, is one of the most complex areas due to the diversity of curricula, the length of courses, and the number of subjects.

At present, universities need to focus on developing a proper understanding of artificial intelligence and how it relates to the learning mechanism, and on creating intelligent classrooms that will lead to the creation of “intelligence-enabled universities.” When universities focus on using the power of artificial intelligence to create economic advantages, the development of artificial intelligence technologies becomes inevitable.

The study of artificial intelligence must proceed on the assumption that every aspect of learning or any other characteristic of intelligence can in principle be described with such precision that a machine can be built to simulate it [5].

The economic and social effect of introducing artificial intelligence into the Uzbek system of higher education is difficult to overestimate. The widespread introduction of technologies based on artificial intelligence into the higher education system will make it possible to move from the export of raw materials to export based on high technologies [6].

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